

Deep neural network with fuzzy algorithm to improve power and traffic-aware reliable reactive routing

Radhakrishnan Murugesan¹, Satish Kanapala², Subash Rajendran³, Prathaban Banu Priya⁴,
Rathinasabapathy Ramadevi⁵, Natarajan Duraichi⁶, Rengaraj Hema⁷

¹Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Annamacharya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Tirupathi, India

²Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Vignana's Foundation for Science, Technology and Research, Guntur, India

³Department of Computing Technologies, School of Computing, College of Engineering and Technology,
SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chennai, India

⁴Department of Networking and Communications, School of Computing, College of Engineering and Technology,
SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chennai, India

⁵Department of Biomedical Engineering, Saveetha School of Engineering, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences,
Chennai, India

⁶Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Saveetha School of Engineering,
Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Thandalam, India

⁷Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Madha Engineering College, Chennai, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 15, 2023

Revised Aug 3, 2023

Accepted Nov 4, 2023

Keywords:

Adaptive load balance

CH selection

Deep neural network

Fuzzy algorithm

Power aware routing

Traffic aware routing

ABSTRACT

In wireless networks, link breaks, and restricted resources create fundamental challenges for maintaining network applications. Several wireless network routing techniques concentrate on power efficiency to expand the network lifetime, but the traffic and reliability parameters are not the primary concern. Though, these techniques are not capable of dealing with the wireless network. Hence, this paper proposes deep neural network (DNN) with a fuzzy algorithm to improve power and traffic-aware reliable reactive routing (PTAR) in wireless networks. The wireless network is formed by clustering by the node power and selects the cluster head (CH) based on a fuzzy algorithm. The wireless node power level, node buffer space, and node reliability to consider the input parameters of the fuzzy system. Then the fuzzy algorithm gives the output for CH round length. This selected CH improves the node reliability, power efficiency with minimized network congestion. Then we use a DNN algorithm to choose an optimal relay by applying an adaptive load balance factor in the network. DNN is a machine learning algorithm, and it provides high accuracy. From the simulation results, the PTAR approach improves the network performance, such as packet received ratio, delay, residual energy, and routing overhead.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Radhakrishnan Murugesan

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Annamacharya Institute of Technology and Sciences
Tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh, India

Email: rmurugesandr@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Several applications and protocols used in wireless networks use connection quality estimations to improve the system's overall performance. However, accurately characterizing wireless connections in wireless networks is difficult since the links encounter regular channel changes and complicated interference patterns. But, it is essential to estimate the quality of the wireless connection to maximize the performance. In wireless networks, determining the quality of a link often involves evaluating the received signal intensity in addition to the error rates. Wireless networks have minimal access to resources, including energy, memory, and

bandwidth. Because low-battery-powered nodes are often not capable of recharging, the amount of energy used by each node impacts not only the node's lifespan but also the network's lifetime as a whole. Therefore, energy is a vital resource. Since the path that uses the least amount of energy may differ from the path with the best performance. In most cases, a longer distance between the sender and the receiving node results in a longer delivery delay [1]. On the other hand, the nodes with the fewest total hops are the ones that use the least amount of energy, but this only sometimes equates to high performance. Additionally, the algorithm needs energy-efficient to increase the network's lifespan [2]. Congestion may have a significant effect on the performance of a wireless network. This manifests as a drastic fall in throughput and an increase in the energy used and the amount of time it takes for packets to be delivered. Congestion management is a vital topic in wireless networks [3]. Congestion might result in a buffer overflow since individual nodes have limited memory. As a consequence, this kind of buffer overflow issue may lead to the loss of essential information, which harms both the amount of time it takes and the amount of energy it uses [4]. As a result, considering buffer space while designing routing protocols is an absolute need [5]. The maximum power point tracking approach is widely used to enhance photovoltaic efficiency since it can produce maximum power under various weather conditions [6].

Problem formulation: using a wireless network makes it possible to ensure fast and reliable delivery of essential data. However, due to unreliable wireless connectivity and the fact that it is being implemented in hostile settings, the data transfer's dependability is reduced promptly. In that case, it may lead to the loss of essential data packets, an increase in energy wasted, and an extra delay. Thus, it is vital to cut down on packet loss to improve the network's performance. Accordingly, developing a routing method that can prioritize accurate data transmission is of the utmost importance. Table-driven routing methods use a lot of bandwidth and need a lot of storage space, reactive routing systems are intended to cut those costs. The dynamic path between a sender and a receiver may be constructed by these protocols using the on-demand applied processes. The power aware routing algorithm (PARA) objective is to enhance the routing established on the power level. This approach develops the details about routes to compute an essential power. It enhances the routing life. However, this approach increases the network traffic and can not provide reliable routing [7]. To solve these issues, deep neural network (DNN) with a fuzzy algorithm to improve power and traffic-aware reliable reactive routing (PTAR) is proposed.

Work contribution: the wireless node power level, node buffer space and node reliability to consider the input parameters of the fuzzy algorithm [8], [9]. The fuzzy algorithm gives the forecasted output like the round length for selecting the cluster head (CH). The main purpose of this paper is to propose a DNN algorithm for solving the optimal relay selection problem by applying the adaptative load balance (ALB) factor that reduces the computational cost. This approach improves node reliability, power efficiency with minimizes network congestion. The remaining parts of the article is structured as described below. DNN with a Fuzzy algorithm to improve PTAR is discussed in section 2. The results of the simulations are presented in section 3. Finally, the conclusion is presented in section 4.

Power is an essential need for the network at all times. Because of this, one of the key performance objectives of such networks is to cut down as much as possible on the amount of power needed by each message. It extends the period during which a gadget powered by a battery can work before the infrastructure has to be maintained. Developing the channels' active time is necessary to convey a complete data package. This is because the amount of time the channels are active is limited. Power-saving routing (PSR) algorithm is designed to reduce the amount of power consumed by a network by routing packets more efficiently. This decision was taken after considering the actual channel characteristics, which included multipath fading, in terms of the minimum amount of power used. However, even though the extended PSR approach is suitable for ordinary network situations, it could be better for usage in conditions that include hybrid networks. This is because hybrid networks present unique challenges. The minimal power cooperative routing technique (MPCR) [10] is used to build a lesser power path, which ensures throughput via an optimal path. This is done even though the path may take longer. Nevertheless, one of the potential drawbacks of the MPCR is that there is a certain amount of time before the optimal path to a specific location will be available. This is likely the case because of problems along the way, such as the exhaustion of the available power supply.

An example of swarm intelligence algorithm to generate meaningful global behavior that cannot be done by each person working alone [11]. Richard Stallman is the one who invented the concept of "swarm intelligence". Ant colony optimization (ACO), is a process that imitates the actions of real-life ants as they search for food. It is an intriguing alternative for creating routing algorithms for wireless sensor networks (WSNs) since it has many helpful qualities. These characteristics include the following: To overcome difficulties with optimization, a significant number of research articles used ACO [12], [13]. This discovery has allowed these approaches to become more widely utilized. Particle swarm optimizer with crossover operation (PSOCO) [14] is an optimization approach that has been recommended because it employs not one but two different crossover processes. The ability of the PSOCO to pinpoint the most advantageous node is the source of its power. It considers the optimal route from various vantage points and angles. Power-aware

cooperative routing (PACR) algorithm as a method for determining the most effective route from the origin to the destination. This approach takes into account the power constraints of the network. This approach considers the power level necessary for effective cooperative communication to maximize the likelihood of success in accomplishing its objectives. On the other hand, this was constructed without considering the requirements for a minimal lifetime for this path. Furthermore, the PACR uses the next hop as a metric in its search for the most effective path, yet this strategy needs to generate routes with the greatest potential throughput [15]. To characterize the fading influence of wireless networks in industrial contexts, a three-layer framework has been developed for the impulse response. Experiments that were carried out in a variety of different industrial settings showed that doing so significantly improved accuracy [16]. The Gilbert-Elliot two-state Markov model is used to carry out a study of the packet received rate (PRR). After that, the link quality indicator (LQI) is converted into one of two distinct states according to the threshold established by the previous step. The Gilbert-Elliot model, developed in line with the LQI [17], is utilized to measure the PRR.

Monitoring link quality in the routing protocol for low-power and lossy networks (RPL), also known as the RL probe, offers an accurate assessment of link quality with minimal wasted overhead and energy. The RL probe uses synchronous monitoring tactics and asynchronous monitoring strategies to preserve the information it gathers on the link quality up to date and swiftly adjusts to any unforeseen changes that may occur in the topology. An RL model drives monitoring operations and reduces the overhead [18]. An approach to determining the quality of connections that extensively uses support vector machines and employs several different classes. The received signal strength (RSS) and LQI are estimation parameters, and the connection quality is segmented in line with the PRR. The model can accurately assess the current connection quality [19] by using only a few probe packets. It is usual practice for hardware-based link quality estimator (LQE) algorithms to make use of characteristics like the received signal strength indication (RSSI), the LQI, and the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [20], [21] methods for estimating connection quality use the RSS and information acquired from data packets received to evaluate link quality [22]. Despite this, experiments [23] have shown that RSS is not sensitive to fluctuations in the quality of connections when used in its intended manner. The LQI would be used as a parameter once the connection quality was found to be of a high standard. On the other hand, the LQI values that were acquired via quick links show a much higher degree of fluctuation. The signal-to-noise ratio, often known as SNR [24]. The DNN algorithm can tackle various challenges because DNN can accurately estimate high nonlinear functions despite its relatively modest complexity, it has enabled various exciting applications in wireless communications [25]. The selection of the relay [26] and the assignment of the channel [27] are examples of some of these applications. Since relay selection has the potential to improve throughput [28], researchers have focused a significant amount of their attention on studying it over the past decade. A maximizing strategy is needed to choose the most appropriate relay selection, and accurate channel state information (CSI) is essential [29].

2. POWER AND TRAFFIC-AWARE RELIABLE REACTIVE ROUTING

The wireless network contains a number of wireless nodes and these nodes move freely in the network field. The block diagram of the PTRA mechanism is depicted in Figure 1. Initially, the wireless nodes build the clusters based on node power, and these nodes select the CH by applying a fuzzy algorithm.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the PTRA approach

Every node updates channel state information like power level, buffer space, and link reliability. The fuzzy algorithm produces the round length (RL) output. Then we use the DNN algorithm to select the optimal relay based on adaptive load balance factor to enhance the routing efficiency.

Power level: absent of energy utilization management will affect the outcome of unbalanced residual energy allocation among wireless nodes, making origin holes in the receiver node region. Thus, power is essential since it minimizes energy expenditure and increases lifetime. The sender node checks the neighbor node's power level during route discovery based on the route request (RREQ) packet. The node power level (PL) computation is given (1). Where, IE designates an initial energy, the residual energy is depicted by RE, as well as TE refers the transmission energy.

$$PL = \exp \left[\frac{1}{\frac{1+(IE-(RE-TE))}{IE}} \right] \tag{1}$$

Buffer space: in a wireless network, the node buffer size is restricted, and the buffer cannot extend size when presenting the highest data packet. For that reason, the node loses a particular amount of data packets; hence, it causes delay and packet retransmission. To avoid this issue, before data transmission, checks the buffer space. Normalized buffer space (NBS) denotes the ratio between the buffer's space and size. It evades the packets waiting for a long time in the queue. NBS computation is given (2).

$$NBS = \frac{Buffer\ Space}{Buffer\ Size} \tag{2}$$

Node reliability: node reliability (NR) is a significant component since time data forwarding suffers from disconnection of the link. It creates an additional delay, energy utilization and retransmits the data. Thus, link reliability-based data transmission to improve the routing efficiency. The NR computation is given (3).

$$NR = \frac{1}{FTR \times RTR} \tag{3}$$

FTR indicates the forward transmission ratio that represents the feasibility of a packet effectively recognized, and the reverse transmission ratio (RTR) that means the feasibility in which the Acknowledgement packet is effectively identified.

2.1. Fuzzy algorithm-based CH selection

The clustering concept is used to improve energy efficiency. Here, the CH nodes are chosen by the fuzzy algorithm based on node energy, NR, and node buffer size parameters. Here, NR and node energy and node buffer size values are specified as the input, giving the output is RL. The RL selection ratio calculation is specified (4).

$$RL = Highest(round[RL_{highest} * Fuzzy(NR, NB, NE)], 1) \tag{4}$$

Every node has informed the value of RL highest, and the highest RL value node is selected as a CH. The fuzzy set reports the node reliability input variables are very high, high, middle, low, and very low. The node energy input variables are very high, high, middle, low and very low. Furthermore, the buffer availability fuzzy input variables are very high, high, middle, low, and very low. The RL output variables are very high, high, middle, low, and very low.

ALB: the greatest data flow is insufficient to the link's capability, creating a bottleneck. Hence packet loss occurs. So, we select the route that equates the load based on the ALB factor. The ALB factor calculation assists in minimizing the clustering network traffic and enhances the network performance. The ALB factor for each route calculation is given (5).

$$N_{ALB} = \left[C_{OH} + P_{OH} + \frac{TB}{DT} \right] \frac{1}{1-\beta_{TS}} \tag{5}$$

Where OH_C denotes the channel overhead, OH_P denotes the protocol overhead, DT denotes the data transmission, TB represents the test frame bits and β_{TS} denotes the calculating time of transmission state. For example, Figure 2 explains source B selects the route based on the ALB factor. In this figure, node B is a source, D is a destination, and X, Y, and Z nodes are intermediate nodes.

Figure 2. ALB factor illustration

The node K to U builds the routes are $K \rightarrow Y \rightarrow U$, $B \rightarrow X \rightarrow U$ and $K \rightarrow Z \rightarrow U$ and these route whole ALB factor loads are 0.9, 0.7 and 0.6. In route $K \rightarrow X \rightarrow U$ in which $X \rightarrow U$ is greater; accordingly, traffic will happen at node X, which makes the packet drop. Alternatively, the route $K \rightarrow Z \rightarrow U$ load is uniform; as a result, the packet drop is minimized. The load balance threshold can be defined as in (6). Where, TH_{ALB} represents the threshold of adaptative load balance and $N_{ALB}(i)$ represents the route adaptative load balance.

$$TH_{ALB} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (N_{ALB}(i)) \tag{6}$$

2.2. DNN based relay selection

The DNN algorithm measures the weight, which can be intended as the function of mapping. The features of input rearrange as a vector that is specified in (7). Then it computes the weight based on the adaptive load balance factor. The DNN algorithm obtains the modified input weights and then computes the output for selecting the relay nodes and this output calculation is specified in (8).

$$X^{(m)} = [x_{PL}, x_{NBS}, x_{NR}] \tag{7}$$

$$Y = N_{ALB} > TH_{ALB} \tag{8}$$

Where, the Y value is introduced between 0 to 1 and the preset threshold value is 0.5. The DNN algorithm based relay selection to enhance the route dependability and and power level.

3. SIMULATION ANALYSIS

Here, the network simulator tool is used for evaluating the network performance. This section exists packet received ratio, routing overhead, delay, and residual energy parameters to demonstrate the achievable performance of the introduced PTAR approach. This research is performed by raising the wireless nodes from 20 to 100 nodes. Table 1 illustrates the simulation parameters of the PTAR approach.

Table 1. Simulation parameters of the PTAR approach

Parameters	values
Time for simulation	200 seconds
Channel	Wireless
Wireless nodes	100
MAC	802.11
Transmission range	180 meter
Range of transmission	150 meter
Simulation region	800×900 m ²
Size of the packet	1024 bytes
Bandwidth	11 Mbps
Rate of flow	128 kbps

Packet received ratio is the ratio between the number of packets effectively obtained by the receiver and the overall amount of data packets forwarded by the sender nodes. Routing overhead is defined as the ratio of control packets created to the number of effectively obtained data packets. The network is realistically congested because of the highest load and the reasonably high wireless nodes. Figure 3 illustrates the packet received ratio of PARA and PTAR approaches based on wireless node count. The routing overhead of the PARA and PTAR approaches is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Packet received ratio of PARA and PTAR approaches

Figure 4. Routing overhead of PARA and PTAR approaches

From Figure 3, when the wireless node count increases, the packet received ratio of the PARA approach is highly decreased; however, the PTAR approach is slightly reduced since the proposed mechanism chooses the best relay node by node reliability, node power level, and node buffer space. From Figure 4, the fuzzy algorithm-based CH selection is minimized the network load. The DNN algorithm predicts the relay is minimized the network traffic since it selects the relay by the ALB factor. As a result, the PTAR approach minimized the routing overhead. But, the PARA approach only concentrates on energy efficiency. The delay metric is a significant since it minimizes network congestion. Figure 5 explains the simulation result of the delay with various wireless nodes, and it is measured by the millisecond. Figure 6 displays the residual power level of PARA and PTAR mechanisms versus the wireless node count.

Figure 5. Delay of PARA and PTAR approaches

Figure 6. Residual power level of PARA and PTAR approaches

Here, raising the wireless nodes initiating from 20 to 100 nodes. The Figure 5, illustrates that the PARA approach delay rises when the wireless node count increases. Although the PTAR mechanism minimized the packet delay than a PARA mechanismsince the PTAR mechanism utilizes a DNN machine learning algorithm to select the relay, fuzzy-based CH selection reduces the delay in the network. The amount of power residual in the present time is known as the residual power level. From Figure 6, the wireless node count rises from 20 to 100 nodes; the PARA and PTAR approach minimizes the power level. Figure 6 obviously demonstrates that the PTAR approach increases the power levelthan a PARA mechanism because the DNN algorithm picked out the relay based on the power level. Furthermore, the clustering concept minimizes the utilization of power level. Hence, the PTAR approach increases the power level in the network.

4. CONCLUSION

Several issues, for example, power-aware routing, traffic-aware routing, and reliability-aware routing, cause vast challenges in maintaining routing in wireless networks. DNN-based evaluator to solve the optimal relay selection issues by rapidly arriving at the optimal solution. In this article, we introduced PTAR using the DNN algorithm to improve the routing efficiency. The main aim of the DNN methodis to select the best relay and minimize the computational cost based on the adaptive load balancing factor. The fuzzy algorithm gives

the input for choosing the CH by applying parameters like power level, buffer space, and node-link reliability that compute the fuzzy output, such as round length. The highest round length node is selected as a CH; as a result, it minimizes the utilized power. The simulation results demonstrate that the proposed PTAR approach increased the packet received ratio and enhanced the power level. Moreover, it reduced both the network delay and the routing overhead. The wireless network is heavily attacked due to wireless is unreliable. So, we will identify several types of attacks in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Mahadevan and N. Anbazhagan, "An efficient framework to improve QoS of CSP using enhanced minimal resource optimization based scheduling algorithm," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 1179–1186, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v12.i3.pp1179-1186.
- [2] N. Sabarinathan, "An effective method for QoS-constrained work flow scheduling of cloud services," *International Journal of MC Square Scientific Research*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 7–17, Jul. 2011, doi: 10.20894/ijmsr.117.003.001.002.
- [3] E. Jarmouni, A. Mouhsen, M. Lamhamedi, H. Ouldzira, and I. En-Naoui, "Integration of an optimized neural network in a photovoltaic system to improve maximum power point tracking efficiency," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 1276–1285, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v28.i3.pp1276-1285.
- [4] S. Murugan, G. Babu T R, and S. C, "Underwater object recognition using KNN classifier," *International Journal of MC Square Scientific Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 48–52, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.20894/ijmsr.117.009.003.007.
- [5] M. M. Ismail, M. Subbiah, and S. Chelliah, "Design of pipelined radix-2, 4 and 8 based multipath delay commutator (MDC) FFT," *Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 765–768, 2018, doi: 10.5958/0976-5506.2018.00380.7.
- [6] A. Unnikrishnan and V. Das, "Cooperative routing for improving the lifetime of wireless ad-hoc networks," *International Journal of Advances in Signal and Image Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 17–24, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.29284/ijasis.8.1.2022.17-24.
- [7] T. Al-Hadhrami, F. Saeed, and F. Olajide, "Power aware routing algorithms (PARA) in wireless mesh networks for emergency management," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. e0204751, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0204751.
- [8] A. M. Akhtar, M. R. Nakhai, and A. H. Aghvami, "Adaptive power-aware routing in wireless mesh networks," in *IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference*, May 2011, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/VETECS.2011.5956288.
- [9] A. S. Ibrahim, Z. Han, and K. J. R. Liu, "Distributed energy-efficient cooperative routing in wireless networks," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 3930–3941, Oct. 2008, doi: 10.1109/T-WC.2008.070502.
- [10] A. M. Zungeru, L. M. Ang, and K. P. Seng, "Classical and swarm intelligence based routing protocols for wireless sensor networks: a survey and comparison," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 1508–1536, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2012.03.004.
- [11] A. Nayyar and R. Singh, "Ant colony optimization (ACO) based routing protocols for wireless sensor networks (WSN): a survey," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 148–155, 2017, doi: 10.14569/ijacsa.2017.080220.
- [12] P. Deepalakshmi and S. Radhakrishnan, "Ant colony based QoS routing algorithm for mobile Ad Hoc networks," *International Journal of Recent Trends in Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 459–462, 2009.
- [13] Y. Chen, L. Li, J. Xiao, Y. Yang, J. Liang, and T. Li, "Particle swarm optimizer with crossover operation," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 70, pp. 159–169, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.engappai.2018.01.009.
- [14] D. Lu, H. Wu, Q. Zhang, and W. Zhu, "PARS: stimulating cooperation for power-aware routing in ad-hoc networks," in *IEEE International Conference on Communications*, 2005, vol. 5, pp. 3187–3191, doi: 10.1109/icc.2005.1495005.
- [15] F. Qin, Q. Zhang, W. Zhang, Y. Yang, J. Ding, and X. Dai, "Link quality estimation in industrial temporal fading channel with augmented Kalman Filter," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1936–1946, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TII.2018.2859919.
- [16] A. Bildea, O. Alphand, F. Rousseau, and A. Duda, "Link quality estimation with the Gilbert-Elliott model for wireless sensor networks," in *IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications, PIMRC*, Aug. 2015, vol. 2015-December, pp. 2049–2054, doi: 10.1109/PIMRC.2015.7343635.
- [17] E. Ancillotti, C. Vallati, R. Bruno, and E. Mingozzi, "A reinforcement learning-based link quality estimation strategy for RPL and its impact on topology management," *Computer Communications*, vol. 112, no. 1, pp. 1–13, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.comcom.2017.08.005.
- [18] S. Jian, L. Song, L. Linlan, Z. Liqin, and H. Gang, "Research on link quality estimation mechanism for wireless sensor networks based on support vector machine," *Chinese Journal of Electronics*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 377–384, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1049/cje.2017.01.013.
- [19] W. Zhang, Q. Gao, D. Cheng, and H. Li, "RETX route metric algorithm for wireless sensor network of online monitoring system for smart substations," *Automation of Electric Power Systems*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 86–89, 2012, doi: 10.3969/j.issn.1000-1026.2012.10.015.
- [20] R. D. Gomes, D. V. Queiroz, A. C. Lima Filho, I. E. Fonseca, and M. S. Alencar, "Real-time link quality estimation for industrial wireless sensor networks using dedicated nodes," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 59, pp. 116–133, May 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.adhoc.2017.02.007.
- [21] N. Baccour *et al.*, "Radio link quality estimation in wireless sensor networks: a survey," *ACM Transactions on Sensor Networks*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1–33, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1145/2240116.2240123.
- [22] K. Srinivasan, P. Dutta, A. Tavakoli, and P. Levis, "An empirical study of low-power wireless," *ACM Transactions on Sensor Networks*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 1–49, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1145/1689239.1689246.
- [23] T. O'Shea and J. Hoydis, "An introduction to deep learning for the physical layer," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 563–575, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TCCN.2017.2758370.
- [24] Q. Mao, F. Hu, and Q. Hao, "Deep learning for intelligent wireless networks: a comprehensive survey," *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 2595–2621, 2018, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2018.2846401.
- [25] Z. Zhang, Y. Lu, Y. Huang, and P. Zhang, "Neural network-based relay selection in two-way SWIPT-enabled cognitive radio networks," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 6264–6274, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2020.2984327.
- [26] T. V. Nguyen and B. An, "Cognitive multihop wireless powered relaying networks over nakagami-m fading channels," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 154600–154616, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2949081.

- [27] T. V. Nguyen, T. N. Do, V. N. Q. Bao, D. B. D. Costa, and B. An, "On the performance of multihop cognitive wireless powered D2D communications in WSNs," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 2684–2699, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2020.2963841.
- [28] N. T. Do, D. B. D. Costa, T. Q. Duong, V. N. Q. Bao, and B. An, "Exploiting direct links in multiuser multirelay SWIPT cooperative networks with opportunistic scheduling," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 16, no. 8, pp. 5410–5427, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TWC.2017.2710307.
- [29] S. N. Reddy and J. Mungara, "Received signal strength indication based clustering and aggregating data using Q-learning in mobile Ad Hoc network," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 867–875, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v27.i2.pp867-875.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Dr. Radhakrishnan Murugesan graduated from University of Madras in Electrical and Electronics Engineering in the year 1998. His post-graduation degree of M.Tech. was obtained in process control and instrumentation in the year 2004 and in applied electronics during the year 2009. He was awarded Ph.D. in the year 2018. Starting his career as junior engineer in 1998, he has worked in electrical projects of national importance. He stepped into the humble profession of teaching in the year 2009 after more than a decade of industrial service at various levels. Serving in various designations starting from lecturer, then to assistant professor and associate professor, he had taught a spectrum of subjects to both UG and PG level engineering students. The broad area of his research includes renewable energy, induction motors, cascaded inverters and Li-ion batteries for electric vehicles. He has published 18 research papers in international journals and 14 in national level journals. He can be contacted at email: rmurugesandr@gmail.com.

Satish Kanapala received the bachelor's degree in Electronics and Communication Engineering from JNTUH in 2007. His post-graduation degree of M.Tech. in the year 2010 with specialization of communication systems. He is passionate about his responsible position of teaching in 2010 and continuing as an assistant professor. His research interests include wireless communications and MIMO signal processing. He can be contacted at email: satishkanapala@gmail.com.

Dr. Subash Rajendran was born on 4th July 1988 in Rasipuram, Tamilnadu, India. He received his Bachelor's degree in Computer Science and Engineering from Maha College of Engineering, Anna University, Chennai in 2010, Master's degree in Computer Science and Engineering from Sriram Engineering College, Anna University, Chennai in 2012 and Doctoral degree in Computer Science and Engineering at SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai. He is currently an assistant professor in the Department of Computing Technologies at SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chennai. He has more than 10 years' experience in teaching. His research interests include internet of things, networking and block chain. He has published more than 10 research papers in conferences and journals. He is a life member of Indian Society for Technical Education (India) (ISTE). He can be contacted at email: subashr@srmist.edu.in.

Dr. Prathaban Banu Priya was born on 3rd February 1991 in Tamilnadu, India. She received her Ph.D. in Electronics and Communication Engineering from SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai, India. She is graduated from Anna University, Chennai in 2012 with the Bachelor of Technology degree in Electronics and Communication Engineering. She received the Master of Technology degree in Embedded Systems Technologies from Anna University, Chennai in 2014 with gold medal. She is currently working as an assistant professor in the Department of Networking and Communications, School of Computing, College of Engineering and Technology, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chennai, India. She has published more than 20 research papers in national, international conferences, journals including 6 in Science citation indexed journals with 45 citations. She has published 6 patents and received a Grant-in-Aid from Institutions of Engineers (India) (R.6/2/DR/2019- 20/DR2020005) for her doctorate degree research in 2018. Her research interests include Embedded Systems, IoT, artificial intelligence, deep learning, data science, signal processing and image processing. She is a life member of Institutions of Engineers India (IEI) and Institution of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineers (IETE) and associate member of Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE). She can be contacted at email: banupriyaprathaban@gmail.com.

Dr. Rathinasabapathy Ramadevi she completed her Ph.D. specialization on condition monitoring using computational intelligence. Her research interests include instrumentation, condition monitoring, signal/image processing and analysis, applications of artificial neural network, fuzzy logic and wavelet transform. She has more than 25 years of teaching and research experience and authored nearly 50 research articles/books in reputed journals/conferences in these fields. She is serving as an editorial member and reviewer of several national/international reputed journals. She is the member of many international affiliations. She can be contacted at email: ramadevir.sse@saveetha.com.

Dr. Natarajan Duraichi was born in Tamilnadu, India in 1977. She received her B.E in Electronics and Communication engineering from Coimbatore Institute of Technology, India in 1999 and M.E in Embedded system Technologies, Veltech Engineering College, India in 2007. In 2023, she joined in Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, India as an Professor in the department of Electronics and Communication engineering. She has completed her PhD from Anna University. Her current research interests include wireless communication, 5G Networks, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, and antenna design. She can be contact at email: duraichi@velhightech.com.

Dr. Rengaraj Hema currently working as Associate Professor/ECE in Madha Engineering College, Kundrathur, Chennai. She Received her Ph.D. degree from Anna University Chennai, in the Department of Information and Communication Engineering in the year 2021. She has completed M.E. Optical Communication from Anna University, Chennai in 2005, B.E. in Electronics and Communication Engineering from University of Madras in the year 1997. Research have done in the field of optical network, her interests are in the field of communication engineering, optical network and signals and systems. published 10 papers in international journals, presented 10 papers national and international conferences. Resource person for various technical talks. Organized several workshops, technical talks, guest lectures, and workshops. She can be contacted at email: hema.ebin@gmail.com.